

Spectrophotometric Determination of Micro Amounts of Ruthenium(III) with Fluphenazine Hydrochloride and Triflupromazine Hydrochloride

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Fluphenazine hydrochloride (FPH) and triflupromazine hydrochloride (TPH) form red coloured species with ruthenium(III) instantaneously at room temp. in hydrochloric acid medium. The absorption maximum and molar absorptivity of the red coloured species are 500 nm and 6.4×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for FPH, and 510 nm and 6.3×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for TPH. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.2-11.52 ppm of ruthenium(III) for FPH, and 0.5-9 ppm of ruthenium(III) for TPH. The proposed methods offer the advantages of simplicity, sensitivity, stability and rapidity without the need for extraction.

FLUPHENAZINE hydrochloride (FPH) and triflupromazine hydrochloride (TPH) have been proposed as spectrophotometric reagents for the determination of palladium^{1,2}, gold^{3,4} and cerium^{1,5}. However, a survey of literature shows that no attempt has been made to study the colour reaction between ruthenium and FPH or TPH. The present investigation describes FPH and TPH as new sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for the determination of ruthenium.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents: A stock solution of ruthenium(III) was prepared by dissolving ruthenium(III) chloride (M/s Johnson Matthey) in dilute hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) and diluted to 1 litre to give 1 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically by the thionalide method⁶. The stock solution was further diluted to give a standard solution containing 20 ppm of ruthenium. 0.2% aqueous solutions of FPH and TPH were prepared in double distilled water and stored in a refrigerator. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals. A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with stoppered 1 cm silica cells was used for the absorbance measurements.

Procedure for the determination of Ru: An aliquot of the stock solution containing 5-288 µg of Ru(III) for FPH or 12-225 µg of Ru(III) for TPH, 12 ml of 10 M hydrochloric acid and 4 ml of 0.2% FPH or TPH are transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The solution is diluted to the mark with double distilled water, mixed well and the absorbance of the solution is measured at 500 nm for FPH or 510 nm for TPH against a corresponding reagent blank prepared in the same manner. The amount

of Ru(III) in the sample solution is calculated by means of a previously prepared standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium(III) reacts with FPH or TPH in hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric or acetic acid medium at room temperature instantaneously forming red coloured species which is believed to be a radical cation⁷. The sensitivity of the reaction and stability of the red coloured species depend on the nature and concentration of the acid medium. The sensitivity of the reaction of FPH and TPH with ruthenium(III) in four acid media is in the order $\text{HCl} > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \geq \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 > \text{HAc}$. The stability of the red species of FPH and TPH in 5 M HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄ and HAc is 240, 75, 60 and 5 min and 150, 60, 40 and 10 min, respectively. Hence hydrochloric acid medium was selected for further studies.

The absorption spectra of FPH, TPH, ruthenium(III) and red species are given in Fig. 1. The absorption maximum of the red species of FPH and TPH is 496-505 nm and 504-515 nm, respectively. The absorption spectra of the reagents under similar conditions show little absorbance at these wavelengths. Hence a wavelength of 500 nm for FPH and 510 nm for TPH was used for further investigations.

FPH gives full development of red colour instantaneously in 4.0-7.0 M HCl and TPH in 4.0-6.5 M HCl as shown by the constancy of λ_{max} . FPH and TPH do not give maximum intensity of colour below 4 M HCl and undergo slow oxidation above the acid range.

A twelve- and sixteenfold molar excess of FPH and TPH, respectively are required for full development of colour intensity. It is found that there is no

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS
Amount of Ruthenium(III) taken 125 µg/25 ml for FPH and 100 µg/25 ml for TPH

Ion added	Tolerance limit ^a (µg/ml)		Ion added	Tolerance limit ^a (µg/ml)	
	FPH	TPH		FPH	TPH
Fluoride	3000.00	2500.00	Palladium(II)	0.80	0.80
Chloride	4000.00	2800.00	Gold(III)	0.30	0.30
Bromide	850.00	2000.00	Iron(III)	1.00	10.00
Iodide	4.00	15.00	Nickel(II)	850.00	1600.00
Sulphate	4500.00	3000.00	Cobalt(II)	150.00	100.00
Nitrate	5000.00	3500.00	Copper(II)	250.00	350.00
Phosphate	3000.00	1200.00	Silver(I)	1.00	1.50
Oxalate	1000.00	600.00	Zirconium(IV)	180.00	150.00
EDTA	12.00	10.00	Molybdenum(VI)	170.00	80.00
Thiosulphate	1.00	1.00	Vanadium(V)	0.90	0.60
Acetate	2400.00	3500.00	Cerium(IV)	0.30	0.40
Platinum(IV)	10.00	8.00	Zinc(II)	1300.00	1200.00
Osmium(VIII)	2.50	5.00	Magnesium(II)	1600.00	1400.00
Rhodium(III)	18.00	14.00	Uranium(VI)	1500.00	1600.00
Iridium(III)	16.00	18.00			

a = amount causing an error of less than 2%.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of
(A) FPH and TPH.
(B) Ruthenium(III) chloride (5 ppm).
(C) Radical cation of TPH.
(D) Radical cation of FPH.

change in the absorbance if the order of addition of reagents is changed. The intensity of the red colour is unaffected in the temperature range 5-90°.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.2-11.52 ppm of Ru for FPH and 0.5-9 ppm of Ru for TPH. The optimum range for the effective spectrophotometric determination is 0.4-11.2 ppm of Ru for FPH, and 0.8-8.8 ppm of Ru for TPH.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values for FPH are 6.4×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 17 ng/cm² and for TPH are 6.3×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 16 ng/cm², respectively.

The standard deviation, calculated from 10 determinations on a solution containing known amounts of ruthenium(III) is 0.006 ppm for FPH and 0.002 ppm for TPH and the relative error is less than 2%.

The interference of a number of ions commonly associated with Ru(III) has been investigated. The tolerance limits for various ions are given in Table 1. The alkali and alkaline earth metals do not interfere.

Determination of ruthenium in ruthenium alloys: Analysed samples of ruthenium alloys were not available. Therefore, synthetic mixtures containing metals corresponding to ruthenium alloys (Zn-Mg) were prepared and the ruthenium content was determined following the recommended procedure. The results indicate that the procedure described in the paper can be adopted in the analysis of ruthenium in ruthenium alloys of compositions similar to that of the synthetic mixtures.

References

1. H. SANKE GOWDA and K. N. THIMMAIAH, *Revue Roumaine de Chimie*, 1971, 22, 5, 745.
2. H. SANKE GOWDA and K. N. THIMMAIAH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 821.
3. H. SANKE GOWDA and K. N. THIMMAIAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1253.
4. H. SANKE GOWDA and K. N. THIMMAIAH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 632.
5. H. SANKE GOWDA and K. N. THIMMAIAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 869.
6. F. E. BRAMISH, "The Analytical Chemistry of the Noble Metals", Pergamon, Oxford, 1966, p. 250.
7. P. C. DWIVEDI, K. GURUDATH RAO, S. N. BHAT and C. N. R. RAO, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1975, 31A, 129.